

Synthesis of Te-N and Te-Te bonded Compounds

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Te-N bonded compounds are of recent interest¹. Literature reports² the reactions of $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$, containing Te_2^{2+} cycle having delocalised π -orbitals containing six electrons. We have isolated $(\phi\text{C}=\text{N}\text{TeCl}_2)_2$ (Te-N bonded compound) from the reaction of TeCl_4 with $(\phi\text{C}=\text{NSiMe}_3)_2$. We have reacted $[\text{Te}_4\text{AsF}_6]_2$ with Ph_2Te_2 to obtain $[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}_6]^{2+}[\text{AsF}_6]^{2-}$ (Te-Te bonded compound). Reaction of $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ with $\text{Ir}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ did not give clean product.

Results and Discussion

$(\phi\text{C}=\text{N}\text{TeCl}_2)_2$ was obtained from the reaction of TeCl_4 and $(\phi\text{C}=\text{NSiMe}_3)_2$, and $[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}_6]^{2+}[\text{AsF}_6]^{2-}$ from $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ and Ph_2Te_2 . The product from $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ and $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2$ was also isolated.

$(\phi\text{C}=\text{N}\text{TeCl}_2)_2$: It showed a strong ir band at 1549 cm^{-1} (CN). In ^1H nmr spectrum ($\text{DMF}/\text{C}_6\text{D}_6$), phenyl protons appeared as multiplet at δ 7.4–7.6. In ^{13}C nmr spectrum (in the same solvent mixture) carbon of C=N appeared at δ 144.86 and phenyl carbons at δ 127–133. The mass spectrum showed 1/2 molecular ion peak. The fragmentation pattern is as follows: $\phi\text{C}=\text{N}\text{TeCl}_3$, m/z 336 (337.1); $\phi\text{C}=\text{N}\text{TeCl}_2^+$, 296 (301.6); $\phi\text{C}=\text{N}\text{Te}^+$, 233 (230.6); TeCl_2^+ , 200 (198.6); TeCl^+ , 163 (163.1); Te^+ , 130 (127.6); ϕCN^+ , 103 (103), ϕ^+ , 76 (77).

$[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}_6]^{2+}[\text{AsF}_6]^{2-}$: The presence of ir band at 695 cm^{-1} between the phenyl bands ($720, 670\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is attributed to AsF_6^- ion. The band at 395 cm^{-1} is also due to AsF_6^- ion^{3,4}. In the Raman spectrum, the strong polarised line at 224 and weak line at 140 cm^{-1} are due to Te-Te bond³. The hairline thick black crystals of $[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}_6]^{2+}[\text{AsF}_6]^{2-}$ did not give good Weissenberg photograph and were not placed on main X-ray diffractometer.

Product from $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ and $\text{IrCl}(\text{Co})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$: The presence of ir bands at $2050, 1090$ and 695 cm^{-1} are attributed to ν_{CO} , $\nu_{\text{C-P}}$ and AsF_6^- respectively. In ^{13}C nmr spectrum ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{C}_6\text{D}_6$), the phenyl carbons appeared at 129 – 135 ppm . Its ^{31}P spectrum (in the same solvent mixture) showed a singlet as Vaska's compound, but the product's signal shifted 21.98 ppm relative to that of the reagent indicating weak interaction⁵.

Experimental

The operations done in pressure flask, were carried out on vacuum line. Other operations were performed under N_2 . Weighings were done in a dry-box under N_2 .

Te metal, $\text{TeCl}_4/\text{benzil}$, Me_3SiCl , Vaska's compound

$[\text{Ir}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$, AlCl_3 , AsF_5 and SO_2 were commercial products. SO_2 was distilled in vacuum over P_2O_5 and stored for 48 h before use.

$(\phi\text{C}=\text{NSiMe}_3)_2$, $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]^{3,4}$ and Ph_2Te_2 were synthesised by the reported methods.

Reaction of TeCl_4 with $(\phi\text{C}=\text{NSiMe}_3)_2$ (1:1 mol): To a solution of $(\phi\text{C}=\text{NSiMe}_3)_2$ (3.520 g, 20 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (30 cm^3) was added TeCl_4 (5.38 g, 20 mmol) in the same solvent ($\sim 30\text{ cm}^3$) at -78° with stirring under N_2 . It was then stirred for another 4 h. The yellow solution was filtered and solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting light yellow-green solid was dried under reduced pressure and crystallised from DMF, (4.70 g, 70% with respect to TeCl_4), m.p. 215° (Found: C, 24.50; H, 1.45; N, 4.13; Cl, 31.48; Te, 37.82. $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NCl}_3\text{Te})_2$ calcd. for: C, 24.91; H, 1.48; N, 4.15; Cl, 31.59; Te, 37.85%).

The reaction in 1 : 2 molar ratio $[(\phi\text{C}=\text{NSiMe}_3)_2 : 2\text{TeCl}_4]$ yielded the same product.

Reaction of $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ with Ph_2Te_2 : Over a mixture of Ph_2Te_2 (0.180 g, 0.440 mmol) and $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ (0.390 g, 0.439 mmol) in a pressure flask, SO_2 (10 cm^3) was distilled. It was brought to room temperature with stirring and then stirred for 20 min. A dark brown liquid with black solid was obtained. The clear dark brown solution was filtered in the other part of the pressure flask and kept at 1° overnight when needle-shaped black crystals of $[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}_6]^{2+}[\text{AsF}_6]^{2-}$ separated (0.12 g, 21.06% with respect to $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$), m.p. $>220^\circ$ (Found: C, 11.08; H, 0.80; F, 17.34; As, 11.21; Te, 58.98. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{F}_{12}\text{As}_2\text{Te}_6$ calcd. for: C, 11.09; H, 0.77; F, 17.57; As, 11.54; Te, 59.00%).

Attempted reaction of $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ with $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$: $\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2$ (0.100 g, 0.11 mmol) was added to a bright yellow solution of $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (0.088 g, 0.11 mmol) in deoxygenated benzene ($\sim 30\text{ cm}^3$) with stirring at ambient temperature. The colour of the solution changed to orange yellow after 5 min and then to dark orange. It was stirred for ~ 4 h, and the yellow solid that separated was dried under reduced pressure (m.p. $>220^\circ$). It did not give satisfactory elemental analysis for the expected $[\text{Te}_4[\text{AsF}_6]_2-\text{IrCl}(\text{Co})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ compound (containing probably Te-Ir bond).

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